

Pest control and management OTHER PESTS

Rat activity in the deepwater rice area of Bangladesh

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Rats are serious pests of deepwater rice (DWR) in Bangladesh. In Apr to Dec 1982, we surveyed DWR areas of Tangail, Narsingdi, Manikganj, and Daudkandi to learn more about rat activity. In addition to DWR, boro rice and rabi crops — wheat,

watermelon, and bitter gourd — are grown in these areas.

Rat activity was measured by counting active rat burrow openings and recording the presence or absence of rat damage in pre-flood, flood, and postflood periods in fields and along shoulders of the highways that bisect the areas. Snap traps were used to catch rats for species identification. Three 1,500-m² plots were surveyed at each site during each crop season. Plots were 15-100 m from the highway.

Bandicota bengalensis was the only rat species trapped. During pre-flood (Apr

to mid-Jun) rats were found on highway shoulders and in all fields, but activity was concentrated in fields with boro rice and rabi crops (see table). Rats used highway shoulders as their main shelter during flood time (mid-Jun to Sep) and attacked floating DWR plants from there. When floodwater receded, they moved back to the dry DWR fields and made burrows, where they stored ripe rice panicles. The study suggests that rat damage could be effectively reduced by using poison baits and rat traps on highway shoulders during the flood. □

Rat activity in deepwater rice areas in Bangladesh during pre-flood, flood and postflood periods, BRRI, 1982.^a

Site	Preflood					Flood ^b		Postflood		
	Burrow openings/ha			Rat damage		Burrow openings/ha Highway shoulders	Rat damage in DWR fields	Burrow openings/ha		Rat damage in DWR fields
	Highway shoulders	DWR fields	Boro and rabi crop fields	DWR fields	Boro and rabi crop fields			Highway	DWR	
Tangail	2	2	42	-	+	106	+	4	162	+
Narsingdi	0	0	57	-	+	131	+	0	182	+
Manikganj	0	6	53	-	+	151	+	2	215	+
Daudkandi	4	0	46	-	+	86	+	0	141	+
Mean	1.5	2.0	49.5			118.5		1.5	177.5	

^aRat activity was measured by counting active rat burrow openings and by checking the presence (+) or absence (-) of rat damage. ^bDeepwater rice fields had 1-2.4 m water during flood time.

Irrigation and water management

Water use and costs of irrigating rice in Southwest Louisiana

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Southwest Louisiana is a major rice producing area in the United States. Topography is flat with poor surface and internal drainage. Generally, one rice crop is grown annually. Soils range from fine-textured, poorly drained clays in marshlands to coarser-textured, moderately well-drained silt loams along the northern and eastern fringes of the rice area.

An impervious subsoil 30 to 45 cm below the soil surface and a slow rate of surface water runoff cause poor soil aeration and a low soil moisture supply capacity. Rice irrigation wells are 75 to 100 m deep.

We conducted a survey to obtain data on water use and costs for rice irrigation from wells in southwest Louisiana. Specifications and annual volume of water pumped are in Table 1. The annual volume of water pumped — 736.7, 919.2, and

Table 1. Specifications and water use of representative rice irrigation wells in southwest Louisiana, 1982.

Well type	Diameter (cm)	Av well depth (m)	Flow rate (liters/s)	Average area irrigated (ha)	Annual volume of water pumped (million liters)
I	20.3	91.4	126.2	80.9	736.7
II	25.4	91.4	157.7	101.2	919.2
III	30.5	91.4	220.8	141.6	1,287.7

Table 2. Total annual irrigation costs/ha for rice utilizing different power sources, southwest Louisiana, 1982.

Well type	Annual irrigation costs (US\$)			
	Diesel	LP gas	Natural gas	Electricity
I	50.96	50.46	35.59	25.45
II	50.31	49.88	34.84	24.77
III	48.05	47.99	32.99	23.11

1,287.7 million liters, respectively — was based on a gross estimate of about 92 cm of irrigation water applied to rice fields throughout the growing season.

Total annual irrigation costs were estimated for different power sources (Table 2). Diesel and LP gas were the most expensive fuels. Electricity was the least expensive. □

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Soil and crop management

Urea supergranule for alternately wet and dry fields

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Efficiency of applied nitrogen fertilizer must be increased. Recent International Network on Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Evaluation for Rice studies proved that deep placing urea supergranules (USG) at low doses in rice increased nitrogen efficiency in most soils. We tested USG deep placement in fields that are continuously flooded and alternately wet and dry. Rice was planted late in a split-plot design with four replications on a silt loam soil (Aquic Hapludoll).

Deep point placement was superior to urea best split application under recom-

Effect of method of urea application, water management, and planting dates on yield of rice variety Jaya, Pantnagar, India, 1982 rainy season.

Management condition	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
	USG	Urea
<i>Timely transplanting (at 25 days)</i>		
Flooding (0-5 cm water)	5.3 ^b	4.9 ^b
Alternate wetting and drying	4.6	4.3
<i>Late transplanting (at 50 days)</i>		
Flooding (0-5 cm water)	5.8	4.7
Alternate wetting and drying	4.6	4.2
Mean	5.1	4.5
LSD 5% USG as urea		0.3
CV		8%

^aUSG = deep point placement, urea = split broadcast. ^bBrown planthopper reduced yield about 15% in USG and 10% in urea treatment (estimate).

mended water management (0 to 5 cm flooding) for timely and late planting. However, brown planthopper damage to the timely crop reduced the advantage of deep placed USG over broadcast urea.

When fields were intermittently wet

and dry, rice yield was reduced for both fertilizer application methods. In this experiment, deep placement of USG had no advantage over broadcast application in alternatively wet and dry fields (see table). Work on this subject is continuing.

Integrating brackish water aquaculture with rice cultivation on coastal saline soils

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Only one rice crop, usually during kharif, is grown in areas with coastal saline soils in India. Land usually remains fallow for the rest of the year because of high soil salinity and lack of good irrigation water. We studied the efficiency of short-term brackish water aquaculture during the

summer fallow assisted by saline tidal water from nearby estuaries and its effect on the yield of the subsequent kharif rice crop. Possible freshwater aquaculture was also studied.

We used two 0.01 5-ha rice plots at the RRS, CSSRI, Canning, on a low-lying coastal area of West Bengal. In Apr 1982 rice plots were filled with saline tidal water from the nearby river using a sluice gate. Brackish water aquaculture of tiger prawn (*P. monodon*) and mullet (*L. parsia*) was managed for 86 d, until Jun 1982. Aquaculture yielded an average 0.65 t of fish and prawn/ha (see table). Water salinity of the culture system varied from 12.5 to 40.0 mmho/cm, which increased soil salinity from 7.8 mmho/cm

Salinity cycle in brackish water rice and fish culture system.